

UniPilot: Enabling GPS-Denied Autonomy Across Embodiments

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Fig. 1. Exploded view of the UniPilot module, with hardware, sensing, and compute components highlighted, alongside an image of the aerial platform that integrates the module in a process tank environment.

Abstract—This paper presents UniPilot, a compact hardware-software autonomy payload that can be integrated across diverse robot embodiments to enable autonomous operation in GPS-denied environments. The system integrates a multi-modal sensing suite including LiDAR, radar, vision, and inertial sensing for robust operation in conditions where uni-modal approaches may fail. UniPilot runs a complete autonomy software comprising multi-modal perception, exploration and inspection path planning, and learning-based navigation policies. The payload provides robust localization, mapping, planning, and safety and control capabilities in a single unit that can be deployed across a wide range of platforms. A large number of experiments are conducted across diverse environments and on a variety of robot platforms to validate the mapping, planning, and safe navigation capabilities enabled by the payload.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the progressing rise of autonomy, it becomes increasingly more important to be able to test a wide variety of complex methods and systems on easily re-creatable platforms. Especially of interest is to investigate and demonstrate a method’s generality across different robot embodiments. Furthermore, the demand for autonomy in different robot actualization and in varied environments necessitates flexibility at the core of this design philosophy. This has become clear with the rise of multi-system solutions considered for difficult challenges in autonomy [1], [2]. As such, these robots need to integrate an appropriate sensing suite that facilitates perception in the environments of interest and a computing system capable of running the autonomy software. Designing such a payload requires careful consideration of sensor selection and placement, computing requirements, power limitations, and weight restrictions.

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Motivated by the above, we present a plug-and-play autonomy payload called UniPilot. UniPilot is a hardware-software payload that can be integrated on aerial or ground robots for autonomous operations. The module is designed with autonomy at its core. UniPilot carries a multi-modal sensing suite integrating visual cameras, LiDAR, radar, Time of Flight (ToF) sensor, and an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), as well as an NVIDIA Jetson Orin NX compute board that runs the autonomy software comprising the multi-modal Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) solution, exploration and inspection path planning, and learned navigation policies. The compute and sensing capabilities allow users to test a wide range of methods while the compact and lightweight design of UniPilot enables deployment across a variety of aerial and ground robots.

UniPilot is extensively tested on a collision-tolerant aerial platform, a legged robot, and a hybrid Vertical Take-Off and Landing (VTOL) platform across a diverse set of environments. Specifically, we demonstrate the performance of the SLAM solution in a high-speed (up to 14 m/s) scenario and the use of multi-modality using a collision-tolerant quadrotor. Furthermore, the SLAM performance is evaluated on the hybrid VTOL platform. Additionally, a mission demonstrating the learning-based navigation policy for safe navigation is presented. Finally, autonomous exploration and inspection missions are performed in a natural mine and two industrial environments with the collision-tolerant aerial robot, and autonomous exploration of an urban underground environment is achieved using a legged robot, demonstrating the autonomy readiness of UniPilot.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Related works are presented in Section II. Section III describes the system design, including the hardware design and the components of the autonomy software. Experiments and deployments of UniPilot onboard various robots are presented in Section IV. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. RELATED WORK

With the increased interest in the deployment of autonomous robots for different missions, there has been an increased need for sensing and autonomy payloads in research and industry [3], [4]. These payloads provide varying capabilities ranging from pure sensing [5], integrated SLAM solution [6], to providing full autonomy capabilities [7].

Early works in this domain include the development of plug-and-play synchronized stereo cameras, and IMU systems that provided out-of-the-box visual SLAM capabilities [6], [8]. As perception is being tested in incrementally more difficult environments, the necessity for multi-modal sensing becomes evident [2]. As such, the payloads follow suit and integrate a wider array of sensing modalities. [5] presents the open-hardware time synchronization unit, EverySync, along with a LiDAR, IMU, and camera payload synchronized with EverySync. [3] presents a sensing payload consisting of multiple LiDARs, stereo cameras, IMUs, and details the design procedure behind building such a payload. The payload CatPack is a perception payload consisting of RGB and thermal cameras, and a rotating LiDAR for Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGV). Leica Geosystems BLK2Go is a commercial handheld mapping unit that integrates 3 cameras, an IMU, and an 830 nm laser scanner with 3 mm accuracy.

Going beyond purely sensing or SLAM payloads, a set of solutions also provide autonomy capabilities. Hovermap [7] presents a rotating LiDAR-based mapping payload for handheld or Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) mounted operations. Hovermap provides collision-avoidance functionality along with waypoint following with its integrated LiDAR SLAM. Similarly, Alphasense Autonomy [9] presents a synchronized multi-camera, IMU system integrating 3D visual SLAM, collision-avoidance, and waypoint navigation capabilities.

The majority of the current works present systems that serve as either a sensing unit – with some providing integrated SLAM capabilities – or with a limited level of autonomy (collision-avoidance or waypoint navigation). Despite the maturity of research in autonomous exploration, inspection, and generally GPS-denied navigation, there is a lack of a unified solution in the form of a plug-and-play module that can provide these capabilities integrated with the sensing and computing unit, while still being an appropriate size and weight such as to facilitate usage onboard small aerial platforms. UniPilot bridges this gap by integrating State-of-the-Art (SOTA) autonomy solutions into a multi-modal sensing and computing unit.

III. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The design of UniPilot is driven by specific requirements for multi-platform autonomy in GPS-denied environments. Key design constraints include: (1) total weight <1 kg for compatibility with small aerial platforms, (2) power consumption <50 W for 30 min missions, (3) operating temperature range -20°C to 60°C , (4) multi-modal sensing with

overlapping fields of view, and (5) plug-and-play integration via standard interfaces.

A. Component Selection

The component selection for the module is motivated by challenges presented to autonomy across a diverse set of conditions ranging from large-scale environments, self-similar geometries, lack of visual texture to those presenting obscuring. A multi-modal sensing suite is employed to enable operation in such diverse environments. The sensors are placed to (1) provide all around perception and (2) ensure overlap between different sensing modalities as shown in Fig. 3. Moreover, accurate surface mapping is considered key for inspection in industrial settings alongside purely visual inspection. To run most modern SLAM, path planning, and control algorithms the module must also host sufficient compute. To enable use on aerial platforms, the weight limit of the module is restricted to 1 kg. Correspondingly, selection of sensors must satisfy the weight requirements and compatibility with the interfaces available on the compute carrier board.

1) *Compute*: An NVIDIA Jetson Orin NX 16 GB module is selected as the compute since it hosts a powerful 8-core Arm Cortex CPU offering the capability to run CPU-heavy software such as perception, mapping and planning algorithms alongside sensor drivers and a GPU offering up to 157 TOPS of performance for performing onboard real-time inference for large neural networks. A ConnectTech Boson-22 carrier board [10] was selected to mount the compute module due to the rich interfacing it provides (Table I) while maintaining low Size, Weight and Power (SWaP) requirements. The carrier board supports four 22-pin MIPI CSI-2 connectors alongside a variety of other communication interfaces (e.g., USB, Ethernet, UART, CAN, I2C, SPI, etc.). The interfaces between the sensors and the compute board is shown in Fig. 4. The power to the module and the sensors is provided via a UWE 12/10 DC-DC Converter capable of providing up to 120 W of power at 12 V.

2) *Cameras*: To minimize the weight of the module, board-level camera sensors using the MIPI CSI-2 interface were chosen. Vision Components IMX-296 MIPI camera boards are used as they interface directly with the selected carrier board. Global shutter sensors were chosen over rolling shutter alternatives to prevent motion artifacts at high speeds. Rolling shutter sensors introduce distortion that are proportional to the product of the speed and the readout time, which are significant at our desired speeds (14 m/s). Two monochrome sensors are placed on the sides with large Field of View (FoV) lenses for all-around perception, while the color sensor is placed at the front of the module for inspection, colorization of mapped surfaces, and providing a live feed to the robot operator (if needed). Additionally for low-light environments, monochrome sensors can be binned to lower resolution for better light-sensitivity.

3) *Inertial Measurement Unit*: The VectorNav VN-100 IMU is interfaced with the compute module using the UART protocol. This sensor is configured to output sensor

synchronization signals to allow precise correlation with the IMU samples. The sensor provides inertial measurements at a rate of 200 Hz. This sensor is chosen owing to its low-noise, stable bias characteristics, and the ability to output synchronization signals at a configurable rate.

4) *LiDAR*: RoboSense Airy is chosen as a low-cost, lightweight LiDAR solution, offering a 96-beam sensor with a $90^\circ \times 360^\circ$ FoV, with a range of 60 m. This sensor is interfaced with the compute platform using Gigabit Ethernet and synchronized with the compute module using IEEE 1588 Precision Time Protocol (PTP), and operated at a frequency of 10 Hz. The selection was based on systematic evaluation of weight (120 g), power (8 W), and vertical FoV requirements. Alternative solutions like Velodyne VLP-16 (830 g) exceed our weight budget, while solid-state options like Livox Mid-360 provides insufficient vertical coverage (59°) for obstacle detection in confined spaces.

5) *Radar*: A D3 Embedded RS-6843AOPU Frequency Modulated Continuous Wave (FMCW) radar is chosen based on its size, weight, FoV and angular resolution, which in contrast to typical automotive radars has larger elevation FoV and equal azimuth/elevation angular resolution. This sensor is interfaced with the computer using a USB 2.0 interface and is externally triggered by the VectorNav VN-100 IMU to maintain tight time synchronization.

6) *Time of Flight Sensor*: To accurately map inspected surfaces at a high resolution, a pmd flexx2 ToF camera is chosen and placed alongside the front-facing camera, owing to the accuracy of range measurements at a short range. Despite a low sensing range of 4 m, the flexx2 sensor is able to perceive obstacles with narrow cross sections such as thin branches or wires, enabling its use for safe navigation. This sensor is connected to the computer using USB 3.0 and offers a high frame-rate (up to 60 Hz).

B. Hardware Design

1) *Component Placement*: The UniPilot is designed to be compatible with a wide range of robot platforms that include both aerial and legged robots. At the same time, it can also be operated as a hand-held sensor unit. To enable all-around sensing, the two monochrome cameras with the Vision Components IMX 296 sensors with high FoV fisheye lenses are placed on either sides of the module. These lenses provide a 185° FoV, and the placement of the cameras ensures that all regions around the module are captured. Considering the need for performing visual inspection and simultaneous mapping and reconstruction of surfaces, a Vision Components IMX 296 color camera with a wide-angle lens is placed at the front of the module, along with a pmd flexx2 ToF camera to map the visually inspected surfaces at a high resolution. The radar is mounted facing downward at an angle of 30° from the horizontal plane. This placement is chosen to ensure ground visibility for accurate velocity estimation for robust odometry. The RoboSense Airy dome-LiDAR sensor is placed at the back of the module to ensure that the features in the environment remain within the FoV of the LiDAR while the front of

a robot is facing surfaces at close distances for inspection. Finally, the VectorNav VN-100 IMU is placed at the center of the base of the module to reduce the effects of vibrations. An exploded view of the sensors in the module can be seen in Fig. 1, while Fig. 3 shows the FoV of the sensors in UniPilot.

Fig. 3. Visualization of the sensor FoV from dual-perspectives: (1) Side-view highlighting the FoV of the LiDAR, front-camera, ToF module, and the radar and (2) Oblique-view showing the FoV of all sensors on the module.

2) *Mechanical Design*: In order to be compatible for mounting with a variety of platforms, UniPilot is designed with a standard set of 4 screw holes on the bottom of the module. Designing platform-independent connections allows it to be mounted on a wide range of robots and handheld units. The module is manufactured using a Formlabs Form 3L stereolithography printer using the Tough 2000 resin material. The material is selected for its strength, impact resistance, thermal stability, electrical insulation properties and low weight, offering a good balance between mechanical robustness and weight. The total weight of UniPilot including the sensors, computer, power distribution, cabling, and structural material is 829 g.

The bottom of the module is designed as three perpendicular plates with a top cover. The exteroceptive sensors are mounted on the vertical plates, while the IMU is mounted on the horizontal plate with the DC-DC converter. The vertical walls are also supported by ribs to increase strength and to reduce deformation with loading. The top cover is easily removable, allowing access to the internal components for maintenance and upgrades. 3D-printed mounts for the MIPI cameras are attached to the bottom of the module and placed outwards to ensure that the cameras are not obstructed by the module body or the other components on the module. The top of the module is a single plate that is only used to mount the compute unit and allows easy removal for maintenance.

C. Time Synchronization

UniPilot utilizes different methods for time-synchronization, adapted to the individual sensor's particularities, to ensure that all measurements are timestamped accurately. The module uses the IEEE 1588 Precision Time Protocol (PTP) for time synchronization across Ethernet-based sensors (e.g., LiDARs) and the onboard computer. Furthermore, it exploits the capability of the VectorNav VN-100 IMU to generate trigger pulses at a configurable rate. This signal from the IMU is used to trigger sensors which expose a hardware pin for

TABLE I
COMPONENTS MOUNTED ON THE UNIPILOT MODULE

	Name	Weight [g]	Power [W]	Description
Compute	1x Orin NX	28	25	RAM: 16 GB, 8-core Arm Cortex CPU, 1024-core NVIDIA GPU
	1x Boson-22 carrier board + heat sink	152	13.8	4x MIPI CSI-2, 2x Gbit Ethernet, 1x USB 2.0, 1x USB 3.1, 8x GPIO, 1x CAN, 2x I2C, 3x UART, 2x SPI interfaces
IMU	1x VectorNav VN-100	15	0.22	800 Hz, Accel.: $140 \mu\text{g}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$, Gyro.: $0.0035^\circ/(\text{s}\sqrt{\text{Hz}})$
Cameras	2x VC MIPI IMX296M	4	0.759	Grayscale, Resolution: 1440×1080 , FoV: 185°
	1x VC MIPI IMX296C	4	0.759	Color, Resolution: 1440×1080 , FoV: $118^\circ \times 94^\circ$
	1x PMD Flexx2 ToF	13	0.68	Range: 4 m, FoV: $56 \times 44^\circ$
Radar	1x D3 Embedded RS-6843AOPU	25	7.5	Range: 49 m, FoV: $180 \times 180^\circ$
LiDAR	1x RoboSense Airy	230	8	Range: 30 m, FoV: $360 \times 90^\circ$

Fig. 4. Visualization of the interfaces between different sensor modules (and autopilot) and the carrier board for the onboard computer.

Fig. 5. Visualization of the sampling of visual cameras and radar triggered by the IMU

synchronization, such as the MIPI cameras and the radar as visualized in Fig. 5. The IMU measurements themselves are host-timestamped by the onboard computer, as there is little latency in sampling from the IMU. A buffer of timestamps corresponding to the synchronization signals is stored. The MIPI cameras and radar sensor drivers thus subscribe to the IMU trigger timestamps and solve the assignment problem using knowledge of the exposure and chirp durations as well as an a-priori calibration for approximate processing delays. The ToF sensor establishes its own timestamping through its driver.

D. Autonomy Architecture

1) *Perception*: The UniPilot module carries LiDAR, radar, vision, and IMU sensors, with the intent of enabling multi-modal estimation well-suited for robust performance across environments, despite perceptual degradations. This set was selected as a balance between the weight and power consumption of additional sensors and the complementary nature of the different modalities. For example, radar and LiDAR

have a complementary relationship, as LiDAR can contribute accuracy and mapping density whereas radar can contribute robustness through lack of sensitivity to environment geometry, following [11], [12]. For the experiments in question, the LiDAR and IMU are fused for simplicity using the geometry-only partition of [13]. The output of the low-rate (10 Hz) factor-graph optimization (the 6-DoF pose) is passed as a measurement to a general, high-rate fusion algorithm [14] to obtain an IMU-rate odometry for use by the onboard control.

2) *Planning*: UniPilot integrates the exploration and inspection path planning method presented in [15], which is built on top of the open-sourced graph-based exploration planner (GBPlanner) [16], [17]. Utilizing a volumetric map representation [18], the planner presents two planning modes, namely Volumetric Exploration (VE) and General Visual Inspection (GVI). In the VE mode, the planner starts with no prior map of the environment and aims to generate a 3D map of the given volume using a depth sensor. It operates in a bifurcated local-global planning architecture. The local planner calculates fast, efficient paths to maximize mapping of the unknown volume within a local area around the robot, while the global planner enables repositioning the robot to the frontiers of exploration as well as a safe return to the mission start point.

The GVI mode enables inspection of the mapped surfaces of a given environment using a camera sensor at the desired viewing distance. It utilizes a volumetric map of the environment, obtained through the VE mode or from a prior mission, to calculate the inspection path. A set of viewpoints is sampled at the desired viewing distance from the occupied surface of the volumetric map and connected with collision-free edges to form a 3D collision-free graph. Next, the minimal set of viewpoints providing complete coverage is selected, and the sequence to visit these viewpoints is calculated by solving the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP).

3) *Safe Navigation*: Maintaining safe operations in spite of challenges in planning or estimation, such as insufficient resolution for small objects or inaccuracy due to degraded conditions, is critical for autonomous agents. As such, it is important that the UniPilot also demonstrates this capability. During operation in large-scale environments, the perception and localization algorithms are prone to drift. As a result, the volumetric map information used by the planner may

be inconsistent, causing the paths being potentially planned through obstacles. An additional layer of safety is required to mitigate this challenge. In response to this, the UniPilot is equipped with a reinforcement learning-based safe navigation policy [19] that commands velocity setpoints to the low-level controller. The policy uses partial robot state, a unit vector to goal location, and the raw depth images from the pmd flexx2 ToF sensor. The NVIDIA Orin NX compute module supports fast onboard inference and is exploited for real-time inference of neural-networks.

E. Diverse platforms

UniPilot is designed to be a plug-and-play autonomy payload that can be integrated on diverse robot platforms. Through standardized UART or network interfaces, UniPilot can be interfaced with a diverse set of off-the-shelf control units and robotic platforms. The module is designed to be used as a standalone autonomy payload providing the solution for SLAM, exploration and inspection path planning, neural-network based safety, and broadly capabilities for GPS-denied navigation in a single unit. At the same time it can function as a sensing and computing payload to run custom autonomy software.

We demonstrate the autonomy capabilities of UniPilot on both the custom built collision-tolerant aerial robot (Fig. 6b) and the legged robot (Fig. 6c). The frame of the collision-tolerant aerial robot is designed from a carbon-foam sandwich material. The robot has dimensions length \times width \times height = 0.52 m \times 0.52 m \times 0.24 m, weighing 1.472 kg without the payload. UniPilot is interfaced with the mRo Pixracer Pro flight controller running PX4 firmware [20]. Pose estimates and high-level commands such as position or velocity setpoints are relayed and tracked by the flight controller. The UniPilot module is also mounted on an ANYbotics ANYmal robot using a custom 3D-printed mount (Fig. 6c) and interfaced with its onboard computers using Gigabit Ethernet. Position setpoints are provided to the ANYmal robot platform using Robot Operating System (ROS). The design of UniPilot also enables its use as a handheld data collection unit (Fig. 6a). In addition to this, we present a the operation of the unit on a hybrid VTOL aircraft (Fig. 6d).

IV. EVALUATION

A set of experiments are conducted to demonstrate the enabling capabilities of the UniPilot across a variety of environments. We first evaluate the performance of the onboard SLAM solution in indoor environments for low-speed missions on the legged platform and the hybrid VTOL robot. Next, the performance of the method for high-speed flights is evaluated, followed by a comparison of the performance of the SLAM solution with and without the radar sensor. The performance of the learning-based safe navigation policy is evaluated. Finally, exploration and inspection missions are performed using both the collision-tolerant aerial robot and the legged robot in a diverse set of environments.

A. Robust Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM)

The mapping performance of the proposed unit is evaluated on the legged system and a hybrid VTOL platform. The hybrid VTOL is operated in a quadrotor mode. The maps of the environment and the aggregated radar point clouds are checked for consistency with the environment. The maps are shown in Fig. 7.

Another experiment is conducted to evaluate the estimation performance during high-speed flights. The platform is manually piloted through an open-area of NTNU in Trondheim, Norway. In Fig. 8, the resulting map can be seen in this environment. The onboard estimate of the speed as a function of time can be seen in Fig. 8, which peaks at >14 m/s. The thin features of the windows and vertical beams demonstrate the accuracy of the SLAM framework even at high speeds.

B. Multi-modal estimation

In this experiment, we compare the result of fusing radar into the LiDAR-Inertial system as in [11]. The resulting map from the LiDAR point clouds of the LiDAR-Radar-Inertial system are shown in Fig. 9. The trajectory estimated by the LiDAR-Radar-Inertial system is almost identical to that estimated by the LiDAR-Inertial method, with an absolute translational error of 0.062 ± 0.033 m. However, the addition of radar measurements has the additional benefit of adding resilience against visual obscurants and geometric self similarity as shown in [11].

C. Neural Safety

This experiment showcases the neural safety policy deployed on the UniPilot module, which is mounted on the aerial platform from Fig. 6b. The policy offers a layer of safety to the robot platform using purely raw sensor inputs from the ToF sensor and commanding velocity setpoints to the low-level flight controller. A simulation model of the robot with a ToF sensor is created in the Aerial Gym Simulator [21] for parallelized simulation. A policy based on [19] is trained in simulated room-like environments with floating objects. The network is tasked to reach a goal location across the room, navigating through dense clutter. The curriculum-based approach for environment population is used increase the clutter in the environment as the policy achieves desired success rates. The trained policy is transferred to UniPilot and raw data from the ToF sensor is used. Given a goal location, the policy commands velocity setpoints to the low-level flight controller to safely navigate the environment. This approach does not rely on access to prior maps, and is therefore not affected by accumulated drifts or mapping inconsistencies. The results from this experiment are presented in Fig. 10.

D. Autonomous Exploration and Inspection

This section presents the field deployments of the aerial and the legged platform Fig. 6b carrying UniPilot in diverse environments, conducting autonomous exploration and inspection missions, relying purely on onboard estimation with no prior map or any assumed knowledge of the environment.

Fig. 6. The UniPilot autonomy module mounted on (a) handheld, (b) aerial, (c) legged, and (d) hybrid fixed-wing platforms.

Fig. 7. Mapping results with the legged and the hybrid VTOL platforms.

Fig. 8. LiDAR map created online from the fast flight experiment (>14 m/s according to the timeseries) of the aerial platform in the NTNU corridor environment.

1) *Løkken Mine*: In this experiment, the robot was tasked to explore a section of the Løkken underground mine in Trøndelag, Norway. The robot started in a narrow tunnel section of the mine, entered the open area, and returned to the start location upon successfully completing the exploration. The exploration planner presented in Section III-D.2 was used. The mine presented a low-light environment with changing topology. Fig. 11 (Left) presents the results from this test. A few exploration instances showing the paths and

Fig. 9. Accumulated registered LiDAR point clouds using the LiDAR-Radar-Inertial (Inset: estimated biases of the IMU) fusion and comparison of trajectories from LiDAR-Inertial and LiDAR-Radar-Inertial estimators.

Fig. 10. Overview of the neural safety experiment, showing an instance of the commanded velocity to avoid collision. Point clouds using data from flexx2 ToF and LiDAR sensors are shown, highlighting the disparity with respect to map quality and density.

the onboard camera, the LiDAR and radar maps, and an instance of the robot are presented.

Fig. 11. An overview of the autonomous exploration and inspection missions conducted in the Løkken underground mine, cargo tank in an oil tanker vessel, and industrial process tank environments.

2) *Ship Cargo Hold*: In this experiment, the aerial platform from Fig. 6b was tasked to conduct the volumetric exploration and visual inspection of a cargo hold inside an oil tanker ship. The tank was completely dark, and the robot relied purely on the onboard lights. The robot had no prior knowledge about the environment and was only given the rough bounds of exploration. The robot started in the VE mode, as described in Section III-D.2, and conducted the exploration of the tank. Upon completion, it switched to the GVI mode and calculated a path to inspect the surfaces of the mapped tank. The maximum height was restricted to 3 m for safety reasons. Fig. 11 (Center) shows the results of this mission, including the LiDAR, radar maps, the robot in the environment, one instance of exploration, and the inspection.

3) *RelyOn*: In this experiment, the robot conducted the autonomous exploration and inspection of a process tank inside the RelyOn Nutec facility in Trondheim, Norway. The tank represents an industrial setting, with low-light conditions and low-visual-texture walls. Similar to the experiment in the cargo hold, the robot started in the VE mode, explored the tank, and then switched to the GVI mode for visual inspection. It is noted that the maximum height was restricted to 3 m for safety reasons. The results from this mission are presented in Fig. 11 (Right).

4) *Legged Robot*: This experiment presents the legged robot conducted an exploration mission of an underground environment at NTNU, Trondheim. The UniPilot unit is mounted using a raised platform on the robot (Fig. 6c) to ensure that the LiDAR can see the ground around the

Fig. 12. Autonomous exploration in an underground environment with the legged robot.

robot. An elevation map is built using LiDAR measurements onboard the module and used to prune unsafe graph edges based on the work in [22] to ensure that the robot is commanded traversable paths for exploration. The robot autonomously explores the entire environment and returns to the start location as shown in Fig. 12.

E. Synchronization

A bench-top experiment was conducted to analyze the consistency of the utilized time synchronization by comparing the theoretical sampling rates with the distribution of the actual sampling rates for each of the onboard sensors. An exception is made for the LiDAR, as the Airy does not use a constant sampling rate for the LiDAR point cloud, instead the LiDAR IMU timestamp results are provided to serve as a reference for the LiDAR point cloud timestamp accuracy. The experiment consists of capturing the sensor measurements for a duration of 520s and then post processing them to analyze the distribution of sensor sampling rates. The results, noted in Table II, show that the actual sampling rates have low-single-digit ms errors with respect to their corresponding theoretical values and a low standard deviation.

TABLE II
SENSOR SAMPLING RATES

	Sensor	Sample Time [ms]	
		Mean	Std. Dev.
Misc.	IMU	5.101	0.654
	Radar	100.000	0.986
	LiDAR IMU	5.000	0.005
Cameras	Front	50.000	1.286
	Left	50.000	1.079
	Right	50.000	1.080
	ToF	100.242	0.880

V. CONCLUSIONS

This manuscript presented the design for UniPilot, a hardware-software module design to enable autonomy on robot embodiments across environments with varying degrees of degradation through multi-modal sensing. The hardware design decisions were outlined and the autonomy software utilized by the platform was described. An extensive set of experiments were conducted to evaluate the module mounted on aerial platforms, including high-speed flight, neural safety, as well as autonomous exploration and inspection. Autonomous exploration missions with the legged platform demonstrate the easy transferability and plug-and-play functionality of the module across platforms. The autonomous missions were conducted in different field environments, showcasing the capabilities of the platform in real scenarios.

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